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Globalization And Culture; Assessing The Challenges And Prospects

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ABSTRACT

Globalisation has continued to grow among nations, posing economic and cultural advantage to some and disadvantage to others, notably middle-income and poorer nations such as Nigeria and other 3rd world countries. This paper looked at globalisation and culture in the context of the challenges and prospect of globalisation to the Nigerian cultural heritage and the Africa at large. The methodology used in the study is the secondary content analysis method, providing the chance at critically reviewing existing literatures on the subject matter of the study. The paper found that many facets of Nigerian culture, including language, customs, values, the arts, the economy, behaviour, and social conventions, have been significantly impacted by globalisation, which is characterised by a greater degree of interconnectedness and interdependence across nations. The paper also observed that the detrimental effects of globalisation on Nigeria's cultural identity must be carefully considered. Religious rituals and globalisation are two factors that affect cultural identity (Santiago 2023). This essay made the case for preserving cultural diversity. Indigenous African cultures have been accused of being distorted by globalization. The paper concludes that globalization posed a greater challenge to Nigeria's cultural heritage far more than its advantage. This bases, the study recommended that a multimodal strategy including education, policy intervention, technology innovation, and intercultural interaction is needed to meet the difficulties presented by globalisation. Nigeria can successfully negotiate the challenges of cultural change and preserve its distinctive legacy for future generations by emphasising the promotion and preservation of Nigerian culture while seizing the opportunities presented by globalization.

Keywords: Globalisation, culture, language, economy, social, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Globalisation grew significantly over the 1980s, 1990s, and 2000s, as evidenced by the sharp increases in regional agreements and worldwide growth (Anderson & Obeng, 2020). Yet, ignoring its many facets and difficulties has stoked political opposition and resulted in a shift in favour of nationalism and protectionism (Stiglitz, 2018). Deglobalisation is the other extreme of the globalisation spectrum, which can be slowed down or even reversed. According to Witt (2019), deglobalisation is defined as "the weakening interdependence among nations." Globalisation proponents contend that trade and liberalisation have a number of positive social effects. One defence of globalisation is that it has a trickle-down effect, meaning that when wealth moves from the richest to the poorest, everyone benefits. Additionally, proponents contend that globalisation can boost the host countries' comparative and absolute advantages, factor productivity, positive externalities, and the best use of limited resources (Machado, 2025).

Critics of globalisation believe that in order to preserve national security and global competitiveness, countries must retain control over vital technologies and knowledge (Edler et al., 2023). They also point

out that cultural homogenisation has eroded local culture and identity. Furthermore, they contend that environmental degradation and growing income disparity within countries are both consequences of globalisation (Balsalobre-Lorente et al., 2020). "Free trade promotes wealth creation and technological innovation, but free competition and open borders also expose people, firms, and governments to uncertainty and poverty," claims McCann (2018, p. 123).

With more than 400 ethnic groups, Nigeria is a diverse country with a wide range of people, cultures, religions, and historical backgrounds. In fact, there is debate in modern society about the idea of a global culture made possible by technology. The traditional barriers to the sharing of ideas, beliefs, and cultural practices have been greatly reduced by the interconnection created by technologies such as social media, satellite television, and the internet. As a result, there is an increasing awareness that a globalised consumer culture is influencing and, in some cases, overshadowing some parts of local cultures. Multinational entertainment companies have an impact on the views and goals of regular people wherever they live, according to Duru-Ford (2019). Global "consumer" cultures are progressively replacing local ones. For instance, Duru-Ford (2019) observes that people's sense of community and social solidarity is being replaced by consumer values, while Tuhus-Dubrow (2019) observes that the English language is gradually but steadily eradicating the regional dialect.

According to the majority of analysts on the globalisation of African extract, globalisation has exacerbated poverty on the continent rather than alleviating it. In fact, some of them claim that nearly all of Africa's problems may be attributed to globalisation (Aluko et al, 2016). The impact of globalisation on African culture has been the subject of recent attention. African culture is atrophying due to its dilution, according to Nicolaidis (2015). One market economy, one liberal democracy, and eventually one westernised cultural legacy are the consequences of globalisation, according to some (Afisi, 2008). It is reasonable to be concerned about how globalisation would affect culture because, aside from its profound economic implications, culture is what binds people together. According to Oni (2018), "a society cut off from its roots may thrive for a while on its own momentum but eventually it will wither like cut flowers in a vase." As a result, losing one's culture also means losing one's identity. Because of our distinct cultural systems, this article addresses globalisation and culture with special reference to Nigeria and the rest of Africa.

Objectives

The aim of this paper is to provide clear discussion and understanding on the relationship between globalisation and culture. The purpose is to look at how globalization, not just as a pervasive system globally, but to clearly see how globalization is affecting the cultural system and heritage of the people of Nigeria and Africa.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the paper is the secondary content analysis. The secondary content analysis is a review method of existing literatures on similar subject matter of study. In this case, the paper relies on publications and academic discourse papers on issues related to globalization and culture.

Conceptual Clarifications

Globalisation

Many academics have characterised globalisation in different ways. Globalisation is a complex process that includes the rise of international financial markets that exchange enormous amounts of money at an ever-increasing rate, as well as the movement of global actors such as media empires and multinational corporations, whose influence may surpass that of certain governments (Onyeonoru, 2018). According to Stilgizt (2019), globalisation is the acceleration of development caused by the spread of contemporary technologies, production methods, organisations, consumption habits, and worldviews around the world. He underlined that globalisation is more than just an economic movement; it is a broad sociocultural process. According to Giddens (2021), there aren't many words that we use so often but that are actually as poorly understood as globalisation.

Oni (2017) believes that every study of globalisation should contain a critical and thorough definition of the term itself, most likely in support of this remark. A "muddled or misguided core concept compromises overall comprehension of a problem, while a sharp and revealing definition promotes insightful, interesting, and empowering knowledge, as well as an understanding that helps us to shape our destiny in positive direction," according to him. After researching the majority of current definitions of globalisation, he concluded that they are inadequate and narrow-minded since they conflate globalisation with internationalisation, liberalisation, universalisation, or westernisation. Although globalisation incorporates aspects of the four previously described notions, it is incorrect to define it solely in terms of any one of them.

There are many definitions in the literature on globalisation, and they differ based on the definition's source and point of view. Amiwu (2016) posits that definitions of globalisation may be institutional or organisational, process-, system-, or value-driven, ideological, or a mix of these. According to Oni (2017), globalisation is the process of progress and increased interaction between nations and people around the world, made possible by technological advancements in 141 areas such as communication, political and military power, knowledge, and skills, as well as the blending of cultural values, systems, and practices. He goes on to say that globalisation is not an innocent, value-free, self-determining phenomenon. According to Onyeonoru (2018), globalisation is the process of connecting nations and regions around the world through the flow of information, or communication, which causes changes in the sociocultural, political, economic, and educational systems and structures that already exist in those countries and peoples.

Culture

In order to function as members of a society, people must understand and identify with its culture, which is a body of knowledge that regulates social interactions. Culture is a dynamic phenomenon that reflects a historical process and includes all of a group's expressions (Okpoh & Ugbegili, 2013). Communication is the means by which culture is learnt and passed down through the generations, suggesting that communication and those who facilitate it play a critical role in the dissemination and advancement of culture. The internet and modern digital communication technologies are the dominant forces of the twenty-first century. Since communication channels dynamically homogenise and standardise information, the human factor in the information process has significantly decreased. Emerging communication technologies provide a virtual world where different cultural identities such as new languages, clothing, food, architecture, marriage customs, and other lifestyles appear and change both individual and community identities.

Literature Review

Relationship Between Globalization and Culture

Nigerian culture and globalisation have a complicated and multidimensional interaction that is marked by both opportunities and difficulties (Nicolaidis, 2015). Many facets of Nigerian culture, including language, customs, values, the arts, the economy, behaviour, and social conventions, have been significantly impacted by globalisation, which is characterised by a greater degree of interconnectedness and interdependence across nations. The exposing of Nigerian culture to the international arena is one important component of this partnership. Technological developments, especially the internet and social media, have made it easier for audiences around the world to access Nigerian literature, art, music, and film (Oni, 2017). In addition to encouraging pride and admiration for Nigerian culture among Nigerians and non-Nigerians, this greater visibility has given Nigerian artists and cultural entrepreneurs financial opportunities (Ogunjimi and Abdul-rasheed, 2017).

Additionally, cultural interaction and hybridisation have been made easier by globalisation. New cultural forms and manifestations have emerged as a result of the enrichment of Nigerian culture through the integration of global influences (Ogunjimi and Abdul-rasheed, 2017). For example, many worldwide music styles have inspired Nigerian music genres like Afrobeat and Afrobeats, creating a distinctive hybrid that appeals to people all over the world. The variety of international culinary traditions is also

reflected in Nigerian cuisine, which has developed via the use of imported products and cooking methods. But Nigerian culture has also faced difficulties as a result of globalisation.

Indigenous customs have been marginalised and culture has become more homogenised as a result of the mass media's promotion of Western cultural ideals and products (Onyeonoru, 2018). Traditional Nigerian values are frequently eclipsed by Western standards of success, beauty, and consumerism, which causes cultural deterioration and identity difficulties, especially among the younger generation. Furthermore, genuine Nigerian cultural manifestations may be trivialised or distorted by the selling of culture for profit, which feeds prejudice and cultural inequality (Oni, 2017). Globalisation has affected Nigerian culture in a variety of ways, both economically and culturally (Ogunjimi & Abdulrasheed, 2017). Although it has given cultural industries a chance to flourish in the global marketplace, it has also made local cultural producers vulnerable to competition from multinational firms, which could jeopardise the long-term viability of indigenous cultural practices. Furthermore, the preservation of Nigerian cultural legacy may be further threatened by globalization-driven economic policies like trade liberalisation and privatisation, which can worsen social inequality and marginalise vulnerable populations.

The Implication of Globalization on Nigeria's Cultural Identity and Peace

The detrimental effects of globalisation on Nigeria's cultural identity must be carefully considered. Religious rituals and globalisation are two factors that affect cultural identity (Santiago 2023). This essay made the case for preserving cultural diversity. Indigenous African cultures have been accused of being distorted by globalisation (Yankuzo, 2013). It is cultural imperialism, according to Yankuzo. He attributed the loss of our old diagnostic and therapeutic systems to globalisation, which replaced our precolonial economies with capitalist ones.

The imposition of what Nigerians have come to perceive as sexual pervasion is one of the drawbacks of globalisation. We need a set of values to abide by as the West spreads its civilisations around the world. We need to understand what our culture tolerates or disapproves of. We must be brave enough to decide what we will and won't purchase in the globalised economy while maintaining a clear awareness of our cultural values. One of the reasons President Goodluck Jonathan lost favour with the West was his anti-gay laws from 2014. Similarly, Museveni of Uganda signed the same law in the same year as Nigeria. The law was designed to protect the "traditional heterosexual family" and was the "culmination of a cultural battle" that had started years earlier (Ilesanmi 2016: p219, 220). Numerous African nations are being pressured to embrace foreign Western cultures.

In Nigerian societies, homosexual and gay marriage are frowned upon. Nigerian culture is being influenced by American values and culture. Okorie (2020) investigated how popular American entertainment shows affected young Africans. According to him, American cultures and values that are depicted on television "will distort African values," which will have an impact on other areas of life. The development of identity crises when local cultures adapt to globalist ones is another warning sign of globalization's impact on Nigerian cultures; young people are particularly vulnerable to this interface. It leaves people perplexed. For example, they imitate clothing that is seen inappropriate in African cultures. They apply it incorrectly. As a result, the attire is inappropriate in African communities and inappropriate in Western contexts.

Despite the advantages of economic globalisation, cultural globalization, a byproduct of globalization, poses a serious threat to sustainable development. Many Indigenous cultures around the world have been erased and turned into commodities as a result of globalisation processes that have increased homogenisation and standardisation worldwide. Communities can use cultural heritage conservation as a tool to lessen the effects of cultural globalisation and promote sustainable economic growth when it is supported and implemented in tandem with economic development (Gražulevičiūtė, 2006).

The gap between the value of legacy to local communities and the expectations of global cultures has been widened by the occasional overabundance of insensitive and excessive international tourists to heritage sites and towns. Furthermore, the value of tangible heritage and its position within local cultures and communities have been warped by the possibility of using cultural material as a source of income. Although it is acknowledged that tourism has the potential to bring about social change and revitalise

traditional arts, it also commodifies culture by selectively promoting heritage properties, which has hampered inclusive and sustainable development for local communities and marginalised their needs (Hosagrahar et al., 2016).

When tourism is poorly managed, it can lead to the commercialisation and overuse of public cultural assets, as well as the privatisation of these resources. While the commercialisation of access to heritage resources may result in overexploitation and destruction of heritage resources, much like natural resources continue to be mismanaged, tourism would become "more and more commercial entertainment reducing monuments and urban settings to decoration." Therefore, it was recommended that steps be taken to safeguard heritage, guarantee its utilisation, promotion, and enhancement, as well as to harness its economic, social, and cultural value for the benefit of both local communities and tourists; and evaluate how well heritage and its innate values can inspire and build tomorrow's societies while mitigating the negative effects of globalisation (Hosagrahar et al., 2016).

Conclusion

Since "globalisation is irreversible" according to the course of human civilisation, significant efforts are needed to maintain our Nigerian cultural identity. Globalisation has unquestionably had an impact on Nigerian culture, as seen by the complex interplay of benefits and challenges. Nigeria's cultural environment undergoes major changes as a result of its increased integration with the international community brought about by advancements in communication, technology, and trade. Globalisation has increased Nigerian culture's prominence and encouraged cross-cultural dialogue and innovation, but it has also put traditional values and rituals in jeopardy. Traditional Nigerian customs and identities have deteriorated, particularly among the youth, as a result of the dominance of Western cultural products and values, which are driven by international media conglomerates. These problems have gotten worse as a result of the commercialisation of culture for financial gain, which has also strengthened prejudices and marginalised authentic cultural representations. Additionally, when local cultural industries compete with multinational corporations in the global economy, economic policies brought about by globalisation have made inequality worse and threatened their survival.

RECOMMENDATIONS

A multimodal strategy including education, policy intervention, technology innovation, and intercultural interaction is needed to meet the difficulties presented by globalisation. Nigeria can successfully negotiate the challenges of cultural change and preserve its distinctive legacy for future generations by emphasising the promotion and preservation of Nigerian culture while seizing the opportunities presented by globalisation. Nigerians can create a future where cultural variety is acknowledged and cultural identity is maintained in the face of external influences by working together and taking collective action.

Digital media and technology should be used as instruments for cultural promotion and preservation. In order to present Nigerian culture to a worldwide audience, this entails digitising historical documents, building online collections of cultural artefacts, and utilising social media platforms.

In order to preserve oral histories, customs, and cultural rites for future generations, digital storytelling projects can also be used to record them. Nigeria can reach new audiences and strengthen its cultural voice while adjusting to the reality of a world that is changing quickly by utilising technology.

Building bridges between Nigeria and the international community while maintaining its cultural uniqueness requires promoting intercultural communication and cooperation. This entails fostering collaborations with foreign cultural institutions, organising international cultural festivals, and promoting cultural exchange initiatives. Nigerians may promote awareness and appreciation of other cultures while celebrating their own cultural diversity through reciprocal learning and exchange. Additionally, programs that promote cultural tourism can draw attention to Nigeria's rich legacy, support economic growth, and promote appreciation and understanding of other cultures.

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